

Sannō Shintō

also known as “Tendai Shintō”

By Emanuela Sala, SOAS

Entry tags: Kami worship, Religious Group, Shintō, Japanese Religions, Buddhist Traditions

Sannō shintō refers to narratives, doctrinal analyses and artistic depictions related to the “mountain sovereigns” (jp. Sannō), the deities of the Hie shrine, now Hiyoshi taisha, in Sakamoto at the foothills of Mount Hiei. In Sannō shintō, the identity of the Hie deities is chiefly conceptualised with the vocabulary and semiotic framework of Tendai Buddhism, and in special (but not exclusive) relation to the lineages residing at the Enryakuji on Mount Hiei, to this day the main Tendai centre in Japan. While the first extant sources relating the Hie deities to the Enryakuji date back to the ninth century, Sannō shintō reached its apex as a discourse in the middle ages (12th-15th century), throughout which the majority of the material extensively treating the identities of the deities was collected. More concretely, Sannō shintō can be defined in two ways. In a narrow sense, it only indicates discourses produced at the Enryakuji, mostly mythological and doctrinal, which establish correspondences between the deities of Hie and specific Buddhas and bodhisattvas. Although Sannō is a collective term for the whole host of deities enshrined in the twenty-one shrines of Hie, most often the “mountain sovereigns” are three of them: Ōmiya, presiding over the western compound of the shrines; Ninomiya, presiding over the eastern, and Shōshinji, also a deity of the western compound. In the “strict” definition of Sannō shintō, these are considered as emanations of, or identical to, three Buddhas: Śākyamuni, the main Buddha of the Western pagoda area of the Enryakuji (saitō), Yakushi (sskr. Bhaiṣajyaguru), presiding over the Konpon chudo in the Eastern pagoda area, and Amida (sskr. Amitabha), presiding over the Yokawa area. Such correspondences are sanctioned by monastic treatises such as the Keiranshūyōshū (14th century). At a broader level, however, we can say that Sannō shintō is also made up of discourses on the deities of Hie that do not quite befit the narrow interpretation. For instance, these might be mythological accounts produced at the Hie shrine, touching upon subjects such as the origin and enshrinement of the deities; accounts of the festival held each year for the deities, as well as monastic discourses which do not quite conceptualise the deities within the same correspondences of the narrow definition. In this entry I shall adopt the broader definition for three reasons. Firstly, because the medieval Hie shrines and Enryakuji were closely intertwined from an institutional point of view. Secondly, because the correspondences of the narrow definition do not represent the full extent of the diachronic evolution of Sannō shintō. Thirdly, because the “narrow” definition of Sannō shintō presupposes the “broader” one, especially from a mythological perspective. Thirdly, because textual material that presents the correspondences of the “narrow” version of Sannō shintō often also includes accounts produced not by monastics, but by priestly lineages at the shrines. Such is the case for two of the the texts which are considered synonymous with Sannō shintō, Yōtenki (13-15th century) and Sange Yōryakki (13th century). Taking account of this, in consulting this entry one should keep in mind at all times that Sannō shintō was not a conscious religious group, but a discursive field comprising various mythologies, ritual and devotional aspects, all joined together by being centred on the same deities and the same place. Please note that this article focuses on the medieval discourse on the Hie deities, but not on Sannō ichijutsu shintō, the pre-modern discourse issued from Sannō shintō but focused on the Tōshōgū, in Nikko.

Date Range: 800 CE - 1571 CE

Region: Lake Biwa area, Kyōto and Mt Hiei

Region tags: Japan

Kyōto, Sakamoto, Mt Hiei, and the Lake Biwa area, where the origin tales on the deities are set, and where the festival dedicated to the Sannō deities is conducted.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sugahara Shinkai 菅原信海, *Sannō Shintō no kenkyū* 山王神道の研究, Tōkyō, Shunjūsha, 1992
- Source 2: Satō Masato, “Sannō shintō no kyōri” 山王神道の教理, *Kokubungaku kaiyaku to kanshō* 国文学解釈と鑑賞, vol. 52, pp. 32-38
- Source 3: Grapard, Allan G. “Linguistic Cubism: A Singularity of Pluralism in the Sannō Cult,” *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies*, 14, 2/3, 1987, pp. 211-234

Notes: For a history of the Hie shrine in English see Breen, John, and Teeuwen, Mark, *A New History of Shinto*, Chichester; Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://eos.kokugakuin.ac.jp/modules/xwords/entry.php?entryID=362>
- Source 1 Description: Encyclopedia of Shintō entry by Satō Masato

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Tendai scriptural sources are employed to determine the relation of the Hie deities to Buddhas and bodhisattvas. For instance, where the deities are considered emanations of specific Buddhas and bodhisattvas, oracles issued by the deities are compared to scriptural sources to determine exactly which Buddha or bodhisattva emanated which deity. Tendai doctrine underlies understandings on how the deities act in the world and what kind of benefits they bestow. Sannō shintō has a thriving mythological tradition. Narratives and practices connected to the Hie shrines and their relation to Enryakuji are recorded in collections such as the *Sange Yōryakki*, *Yōtenki* and *Keiranshūyoshū*. None of these, however, offer incontrovertible prescriptions on the deities.

Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Traditions on the deities and shrines, where written, often say that they are reporting an oral tradition, heard from an authoritative figure (for instance, in texts such as the *Yōtenki* and *Sange yōryakki*, this figure can be an elderly *Hafuribe* priest.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: Only insofar as sutras, which are framed as sermons issued from the Buddha *Śākyamuni*, are present at the doctrinal and hermeneutical background of *sannō shintō*.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Traditions transmitted within monastic or priestly lineages.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Editing texts on traditions on the deities is the realm of experts, such as scholar monks or priestly authoritative figures.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Writings attributed to lay people, such as Ōe no Masafusa (1041 -1111) are considered authoritative and quoted as sources, e.g. in the *Yōtenki* and *Sange Yōryakki*.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the extant textual sources on the traditions of the Hie shrines were largely produced by Enryakuji monastics or high ranking priests.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Sannō shintō mythologically relates to other shintō lineages and institutions in different ways. Firstly, on the level of relations among deities. The deities (kami) of the Hie shrine are recounted to uphold family relations with the deities of other shrines, for instance the two Kamo shrines in Kyoto and the Matsunoo shrine, south of Kyoto. The specific relations vary in different sources. In the *Yōtenki* (12-15th century), the deity of Matsunoo is said by one shrine priest to be the grandfather of one of the deities of the Western compound of Hie, whose mother is the deity of the Kamo shrine. This mythological kinship reflects kinship claimed within the priestly groups. A second kind of relationship is of identity. The deity of the main shrine of the Western compound of Hie, called Ōmiya, is considered identical to the deity of the Miwa shrine, in Yamato, especially in sources issued from a monastic environment. This identity is also claimed in sources issued from the kami-worship tradition of the Miwa shrine (see reference for the latter).

Reference: Andreeva, Anna. *Assembling Shinto: Buddhist Approaches to Kami Worship in Medieval Japan*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Asia Center, 2017.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Hie deities each have dedicated shrine buildings and palanquins, temporary shrines were built around the Biwa lake for the festival. In most narratives, specific deities are connected to specific areas and architectural structures of the Enryakuji. For instance, the deity of the Western compound of the Hie shrine, Ōmiya, is considered identical to the Buddha Śākyamuni, and as such presided over the Western pagoda area of the Enryakuji. The main deity of the Eastern compound of the Hie shrine, Ninomiya, identified with the Buddha Bhaiṣajyaguru (jp. Yakushi), presided over the Konponchudo in the Eastern pagoda area of the Enryakuji. Shōshinji, another deity of the Western compound, and the third of the main sannō deities, was identified with the Buddha Amitabha and thus presided over the Yokawa area of the Enryakuji. The shrine buildings (as most part of the Enryakuji) were destroyed by Oda Nobunaga's troops in 1571, so the current shrine buildings were largely reconstructed in the Edo period (1600-1868). The shrine structure (e.g. name of the shrines, identities of the deities enshrined) was also dramatically reorganised in the Meiji period (1868), after the state imposed a separation of Buddhism from shinto. Reference is a video showing the current shrine structures, which can be compared to its medieval configuration in the mandala linked.

Reference: びわ湖大津観光協会 Biwako Otsu Tourism Association, Shiga. “日吉大社 Hiyoshi Taisha Shrine”. YouTube, December 9, 2010. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9AnIN5allpY>.

Reference: Nara National Museum. “Important Cultural Property Mandala of Hie Sannō Shrine (J., Sannō Miya Mandara) Hanging Scroll; Ink and Colors on Silk H 120.7, W 68.1 Muromachi Period 15th Century”. Nara National Museum, n.d.. <https://www.narahaku.go.jp/english/collection/v-732-0.html>.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Hie shrines were completely burned by Oda Nobunaga in 1571, it is thus difficult to know their medieval surface area. However, we do have medieval depictions of the shrines. The landscape of the shrine area appears in mandalas which focus on the shrine structure- a depiction of sacred spaces which was popularised throughout the middle ages.

Reference: Otsu City Museum of History. “日吉の神と祭”. Otsu City Museum of History, n.d..

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure. However, an idea (for the space occupied by shrine buildings within the precincts of the Hie shrine) can be garnered from the mandala linked above.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to pinpoint adherents, as sannō shintō was a discourse to which one could participate with various levels of involvement (by contributing narratives, performing rituals with a high or low religious ranking, participating to the festival as a lay attendant or member of audience, financially sustaining the festival...). If we look at those who manipulated narratives, scholarship largely assigns this role to one monastic lineage of scholar monks at the Enryakuji, called kike. There are no quantitative studies on this lineage, further complicated by the fact that kike could also belong to other lineages at the same time and we do not know what percentage of the "three thousand monks" of the medieval Enryakuji actively participated in the sannō cult. If we extend the count to high ranking priests at the Hie shrine, who were involved in the production of documents on the deities, the Yōtenki (12-15th century) reports that there are thirty "current" shrine attendants (shashi) under the shrine's high priest (negi) in 1223. It is more difficult to determine the numbers of the lower ranking priests at the shrines, but sources on the matsuri talk about hundreds of people involved in skirmishes. Hundreds of people were reported to participate in the festival and sermons on the deities.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: There is an ordination platform for Tendai monastics and high ranking priests are hereditary, but there is no affiliation procedure for those who worship at the shrine or attend the festival.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Only in the case of high ranking priests at the Hie shrine (Hafuribe family) and only in the sense that their position (for instance as high priest, or negi) is hereditary.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Hafuribe family belongs to a group of priestly families. No such thing for laypeople worshipping at the shrine (in which case affiliation is not required).

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: But monastics and priests are overwhelmingly male, while there are oracular roles at the shrine which employ the expertise of shamanesses.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that Enryakuji monastics have ritual initiations (kanjō) whereby they are affiliated to one or many specific tradition (in this case within Tendai), and there exists a sannō kanjō and other ones related to, among other things, knowledge of kami matters.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Legends on ancestors of priestly lineages tell how their role came about after a manifestation of the deity.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Temporary architecture. Temporary shrines erected during the festival, to host the palanquins of the deities in the precincts of shrines (e.g. Karasaki on the Biwa lake).

Notes: Also, shrine buildings and temple buildings are different. Shrine precincts are clearly delimited with gates (torii).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The primary aim of the Enryakuji/Hie shrine is to protect the imperial palace and the "state". High ranking priests at the shrines from the Hafuribe family are part of an official priestly ranking sanctioned by the Bureau of kami matters (jingikan). The shrine received imperial donations as part of an imperially-sanctioned system of twenty-two shrines with state sponsorship. Monastic rank (sōi) was also sanctioned by the polity. In the Heian period, monastic expeditions to China were funded by the government. This, however, does not mean that the government supported "sannō shintō", and relates more broadly to the institutional landscape from which sannō shintō issued but of which it is one aspect.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Hie shrine received imperial offerings.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, but sometimes unclear.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Also in religious private space. Figurines of the deities are hidden from view.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Sannō mandala are representations of the Sannō deities (or some of them), and/or the shrine precincts. Present in private and public spaces, commissioned by devotees and religious specialists.

Reference: Arichi, Meri. "Hie-sannō Mandara: The Iconography of Kami and Sacred Landscape in Medieval Japan". PhD dissertation, SOAS University of London, 2002.

Reference: Otsu City Museum of History. "日吉の神と祭". Otsu City Museum of History, n.d.. <http://www.rekihaku.otsu.shiga.jp/news/1104.html>.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Monkeys are the messengers of the Hie deities, feature prominently in depictions of shrines. One of the Hie deities, Daigyōji, is often represented as one in mandalas.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Notes: No, but mount Hiei (where the Enryakuji is located) and mount Hachioji (the small peak in the shrine precinct) feature prominently in iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Deities represented as specific Buddhas and bodhisattvas, of which they are the emanation/with whom they are identified.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Deities represented as Buddhist monastics, Japanese courtiers and in Chinese habit.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Representation of shrines and shrine area as a sacred space.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

|

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The shrine buildings constituting the Hie shrine are sprawled over the area at the foothills of a small peak, called Mount Hachiōji (381 meters), on whose top are two shrines, Sannomiya and Ushio. The peak features prominently in iconography, and is often equated to the Vulture peak of Buddhist scriptures. Mt Hiei and its mountain range also feature prominently in discourses related to the Hie deities, as a site of worship and apparition. Lake Biwa has a prominent role in legends as the apparition site of some of the sannō deities, but notably of the most important one, the deity of the Western compound Ōmiya. The palanquins of the deities were (and are) transported on the lake by boat during the festival.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is not a sannō shintō- specific structure, but Tendai hierarchies apply. Priestly hierarchies at the Hie shrine sanctioned by the Council of kami affairs (jingikan).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The act of going to the Hie shrine is highly emphasised.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

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– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

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– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Hafuribe family belongs to a group of priestly families. No such thing for laypeople worshipping at the shrine (in which case affiliation is not required).

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– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

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Notes: But monastics and priests are overwhelmingly male, while there are oracular roles at the shrine which employ the expertise of shamanesses.

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Notes: In the sense that Enryakuji monastics have ritual initiations (kanjō) whereby they are affiliated to one or many specific tradition (in this case within Tendai), and there exists a sannō kanjō and other ones related to, among other things, knowledge of kami matters.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Legends on ancestors of priestly lineages tell how their role came about after a manifestation of the deity.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The primary aim of the Enryakuji/Hie shrine is to protect the imperial palace and the "state". High ranking priests at the shrines from the Hafuribe family are part of an official priestly ranking sanctioned by the Bureau of kami matters (jingikan). The shrine received imperial donations as part of an imperially-sanctioned system of twenty-two shrines with state sponsorship. Monastic rank (sōi) was also sanctioned by the polity. In the Heian period, monastic expeditions to China were funded by the government. This, however, does not mean that the government supported "sannō shintō", and relates more broadly to the institutional landscape from which sannō shintō issued but of which it is one aspect.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Hie shrine received imperial offerings.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, but sometimes unclear.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to pinpoint adherents, as sannō shintō was a discourse to which one could participate with various levels of involvement (by contributing narratives, performing rituals with a high or low religious ranking, participating to the festival as a lay attendant or member of audience, financially sustaining the festival...). If we look at those who manipulated narratives, scholarship largely assigns this role to one monastic lineage of scholar monks at the Enryakuji, called kike. There are no quantitative studies on this lineage, further complicated by the fact that kike could also belong to other lineages at the same time and we do not know what percentage of the "three thousand monks" of the medieval Enryakuji actively participated in the sannō cult. If we extend the count to high ranking priests at the Hie shrine, who were involved in the production of documents on the deities, the Yōtenki

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

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Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is not a sannō shintō- specific structure, but Tendai hierarchies apply. Priestly hierarchies at the Hie shrine sanctioned by the Council of kami affairs (jingikan).

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– Yes

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↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

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↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

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Notes: Traditions transmitted within monastic or priestly lineages.

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↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the extant textual sources on the traditions of the Hie shrines were largely produced by Enryakuji monastics or high ranking priests.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Hie deities each have dedicated shrine buildings and palanquins, temporary shrines were built around the Biwa lake for the festival. In most narratives, specific deities are connected to specific areas and architectural structures of the Enryakuji. For instance, the deity of the Western compound of the Hie shrine, Ōmiya, is considered identical to the Buddha Śākyamuni, and as such presided over the Western pagoda area of the Enryakuji. The main deity of the Eastern compound of the Hie shrine, Ninomiya, identified with the Buddha Bhaiṣajyaguru (jp. Yakushi), presided over the Konponchudo in the Eastern pagoda area of the Enryakuji. Shōshinji, another deity of the Western compound, and the third of the main sannō deities, was identified with the Buddha Amitabha and thus presided over the Yokawa area of the Enryakuji. The shrine buildings (as most part of the Enryakuji) were destroyed by Oda Nobunaga's troops in 1571, so the current shrine buildings were largely reconstructed in the Edo period (1600-1868). The shrine structure (e.g. name of the shrines, identities of the deities enshrined) was also dramatically reorganised in the Meiji period (1868), after the state imposed a separation of Buddhism from shinto. Reference is a video showing the current shrine structures, which can be compared to its medieval configuration in the mandala linked.

Reference: [びわ湖大津観光協会 Biwako Otsu Tourism Association, Shiga. “日吉大社 Hiyoshi Taisha Shrine”.](#)

YouTube, December 9, 2010. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9AnIN5allpY>.

Reference: Nara National Museum. "Important Cultural Property Mandala of Hie Sannō Shrine (J., Sannō Miya Mandara) Hanging Scroll; Ink and Colors on Silk H 120.7, W 68.1 Muromachi Period 15th Century". Nara National Museum, n.d.. <https://www.narahaku.go.jp/english/collection/v-732-0.html>.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Hie shrines were completely burned by Oda Nobunaga in 1571, it is thus difficult to know their medieval surface area. However, we do have medieval depictions of the shrines. The landscape of the shrine area appears in mandalas which focus on the shrine structure- a depiction of sacred spaces which was popularised throughout the middle ages.

Reference: Otsu City Museum of History. "日吉の神と祭". Otsu City Museum of History, n.d..

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know for the medieval structure. However, an idea (for the space occupied by shrine buildings within the precincts of the Hie shrine) can be garnered from the mandala linked above.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Temporary architecture. Temporary shrines erected during the festival, to host the palanquins of the deities in the precincts of shrines (e.g. Karasaki on the Biwa lake).

Notes: Also, shrine buildings and temple buildings are different. Shrine precincts are clearly delimited with gates (torii).

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Also in religious private space. Figurines of the deities are hidden from view.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Sannō mandala are representations of the Sannō deities (or some of them), and/or the shrine precincts. Present in private and public spaces, commissioned by devotees and religious specialists.

Reference: Arichi, Meri. "Hie-sannō Mandara: The Iconography of Kami and Sacred Landscape in Medieval Japan". PhD dissertation, SOAS University of London, 2002.

Reference: Otsu City Museum of History. "日吉の神と祭". Otsu City Museum of History, n.d.. <http://www.rekihaku.otsu.shiga.jp/news/1104.html>.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Monkeys are the messengers of the Hie deities, feature prominently in depictions of shrines. One of the Hie deities, Daigyōji, is often represented as one in mandalas.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Notes: No, but mount Hiei (where the Enryakuji is located) and mount Hachioji (the small peak in the shrine precinct) feature prominently in iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Deities represented as specific Buddhas and bodhisattvas, of which they are the emanation/with whom they are identified.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Deities represented as Buddhist monastics, Japanese courtiers and in Chinese habit.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Representation of shrines and shrine area as a sacred space.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The shrine buildings constituting the Hie shrine are sprawled over the area at the foothills of a small peak, called Mount Hachiōji (381 meters), on whose top are two shrines, Sannomiya and Ushio. The peak features prominently in iconography, and is often equated to the Vulture peak of Buddhist scriptures. Mt Hiei and its mountain range also feature prominently in discourses related to the Hie deities, as a site of worship and apparition. Lake Biwa has a prominent role in legends as the apparition site of some of the sannō deities, but notably of the most important one, the deity of the Western compound Ōmiya. The palanquins of the deities were (and are) transported on the lake by boat during the festival.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The act of going to the Hie shrine is highly emphasised.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Sannō shintō does not have a specific vision of death and rebirth, but is part of the wider Buddhist discourse. However, a favourable rebirth is part of the boons that the deities may bestow on those who visit the shrines.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
 - No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Yes

- ↳ Food:
 - No

- ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Idea of deities disliking death is present and addressed in sources.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: "Laziness" identified in sources as a characteristic of all sentient beings in Japan. The laziness of Japanese people, who are not psychologically prepared to obtain Buddhist salvation with their own efforts, is the basic prerequisite for the appearance of Buddhist deities in the world in the guise of deities. This process is seen to facilitate Japanese people's readiness to embrace Buddhist teachings. This is not an idea specific to sannō shintō, it is common to other medieval discourses on deities (e.g. kami), however it is very strongly addressed in sannō shintō sources.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Buddhist ethical principles also apply (as deities are avatars of Buddhas and bodhisattvas)

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: But not emphasised.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that there is an expectation for a future Buddha, Miroku, to eventually restore the prime of Buddhist teachings to the world. In the Yōtenki (12-15th century), he is identified as acting in the world as a bodhisattva under the guise of one of the Hie deities, Jūzenji. However, "messianic" beliefs are not emphasised in sannō shintō.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Alive in the sense that he is acting in this world as a bodhisattva under the guise of the Hie deity Jūzenji. He is not a Buddha yet, so has not fulfilled his eschatological role.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: If we broadly consider Buddhas messiahs. He is the Buddha who follows the historical one, Śākyamuni.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Political stability comes as an effect of religious stability.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the historical Buddha Śākyamuni in some sources and the Buddha Mahāvairocana in others (though sometimes identified with each other) appear as markedly above other Buddhas. Deities are emanated from them/identified with them (but also with other Buddhas, who are sometimes considered their emanation/identified with them).

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Śākyamuni is frequently recounted to issue oracles in guise of deity, but identified as Śākyamuni.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Dreams

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Deities manifest themselves to selected few. Especially the deity of the main shrine of the Western compound, Ōmiya.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes some of the Hie deities are narrated as part of a family configuration (main deity of the Western compound father of other deity of Western compound), but not strict and not in all sources. Sometimes family relationship with other main shrines in the area (for instance Kamo and Matsunoo shrines).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Shrines are ranked into seven upper, seven median and seven lower shrines. Deities are ranked accordingly. The main deity of the shrines is the main one of the Western compound, Ōmiya.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist pure lands or Buddhist lands are both outcomes described in sannō shintō material.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: Rebirth may happen elsewhere, in a Pure Land or a hell, but it might also happen in this world, with various degrees of success. A successful life in the phenomenal world is part of the boons granted by the Hie deities.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: It is made known through oracles.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Although in some sources the many supernatural beings are clearly framed as being emanated by one Buddha.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Disease or even death caused by wrath of deities, unfavourable rebirth can be a result of neglecting to worship them.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The wrath of the deities can result from an offense to their priests or to the Enryakuji monastics. The person incurring the wrath is not necessarily the one who has committed the offense in the first place. In the Heike monogatari, the regent Fujiwara no Moromichi falls ill as a result of the wrath of the sannō deities. The events leading to the disease are the following: 1. Fujiwara no Yoshitsuna, the governor of Mino province, kills an Enryakuji monk. 2. Some Hie shrine and Enryakuji temple officials petition to the imperial gates for Yoshitsuna's punishment. 3. The regent Fujiwara no Moromichi orders to disperse them. 4. Eight of them are killed. English translation of the episode in McCullough, Helen C., *The Tale of the Heike*, Stanford, California, Stanford University Press, 1988, pp. 49-50.

Reference: McCullough, Helen Craig. *The Tale of the Heike*. Stanford, California: Stanford

University Press, 2014.

Reference: McCullough, Helen Craig. *The Tale of the Heike*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press, 2014.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Although a possibility, appropriate worship of the deities should avoid this unfavourable rebirth.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Rebirth as denizens of hell or angry spirits is a possibility, but appropriate worship of the deities should avoid this unfavourable rebirth.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on sources, but the ones praising the benefic activity of the Hie deities as agents of Buddhas emphasise the blanket character of their benevolence, no matter how much of a desperate case the person seeking help is.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in Heian-period sources (794-1185).

Reference: Satō 佐藤, Masato 真人. ““heian Shoki Tendaishū No Shinbutsu Shūgō: Saichō to Ennin Wo Chūshin Ni” 平安初期天台宗の神仏習合思想—最澄と円珍を中心に—”. In *Umi Wo Wataru Tendai Bunka 海を渡る天台文*. Tōkyō: Bensei Shuppan, 2008.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: We might say there is an eschatology ONLY in the sense that Miroku exists. My answer is negative because there is no emphasis in the material on the coming of future Buddhas. Even more so because, within a context of correct worship, the Hie shrines are already, in the phenomenal world, a Buddhist Pure Land.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See additional questions. It is important to note that virtues are not always expected to be upheld by those who worship at the Hie shrines. On the contrary, a certain kind of wretchedness is framed as expected from them. This is because 1. Discourses on the position of Japan in the Buddhist world at the time rather considered Japan a "desperate case", where the consciences of its inhabitants were unsuited to receive Buddhist teachings. This was because of their temporal and spatial distance from the "prime time" of Buddhism, when Śākyamuni was active in the world. Some discourses connected to sannō shintō (but not all) emphasise this first aspect. 2. The Hie shrine is framed (e.g. in the Yōtenki 12th-15th century) as being especially powerful because of its capacity to bring benefit to people who might be considered "hopeless", for instance because they are especially poor and cannot donate large amounts of money or because they have various physical issues as a result of their karmic hindrances.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– No

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as compassion is a primary Mahayana virtue it is highly emphasised, however it is mostly the compassion of the deities which is essential to achieve salvation.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

Notes: These are all virtues emphasised as belonging to the deities, but not necessarily required of the adherents.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Giving alms to the shrines grants benefits in this life or the next.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar selfless giving is a Mahayana principle.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual adherence: going to the Hie shrines and giving offers is seen as the way to obtain worldly and otherworldly benefits (for instance ensuring one a favourable rebirth in a Buddhist paradise). However, the ritual in question might be as simple as giving alms or offerings.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– No

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: These are more described as ideal outcome of worshipping the deities.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– No

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the mercy of the deities and the benefits they bestow are seen (and written about) as "something to be thankful for".

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Though it is a positive outcome of good karma and correct worship (e.g. in Yōtenki, 13-15th century).

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Notes: It depends. For priests at the shrine, ideally yes, but for worshippers, no.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Sannō shintō does not have a specific vision of death and rebirth, but is part of the wider Buddhist discourse. However, a favourable rebirth is part of the boons that the deities may bestow on those who visit the shrines.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist pure lands or Buddhist lands are both outcomes described in sannō shintō material.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: Rebirth may happen elsewhere, in a Pure Land or a hell, but it might also happen in this world, with various degrees of success. A successful life in the phenomenal world is part of the boons granted by the Hie deities.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Although a possibility, appropriate worship of the deities should avoid this unfavourable rebirth.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Rebirth as denizens of hell or angry spirits is a possibility, but appropriate worship of the deities should avoid this unfavourable rebirth.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the historical Buddha Śākyamuni in some sources and the Buddha Mahāvairocana in others (though sometimes identified with each other) appear as markedly above other Buddhas. Deities are emanated from them/identified with them (but also with other Buddhas, who are sometimes considered their emanation/identified with them).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do

(future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Śākyamuni is frequently recounted to issue oracles in guise of deity, but identified as Śākyamuni.

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: Dreams

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

- No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

- Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

- Yes

Notes: Deities manifest themselves to selected few. Especially the deity of the main shrine of the Western compound, Ōmiya.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

- Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

- Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sometimes some of the Hie deities as narrated as part of a family configuration (main deity of the Western compound father of other deity of Western compound), but not strict and not in all sources. Sometimes family relationship with other main shrines in the area (for instance Kamo and Matsunoo shrines).
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Shrines are ranked into seven upper, seven median and seven lower shrines. Deities are ranked accordingly. The main deity of the shrines is the main one of the Western compound, Ōmiya.
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Idea of deities disliking death is present and addressed in sources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: "Laziness" identified in sources as a characteristic of all sentient beings in Japan. The laziness of Japanese people, who are not psychologically prepared to obtain Buddhist salvation with their own efforts, is the basic prerequisite for the appearance of Buddhist deities in the world in the guise of deities. This process is seen to facilitate Japanese people's readiness to embrace Buddhist teachings. This is not an idea specific to sannō shintō, it is common to other medieval discourses on deities (e.g. kami), however it is very strongly addressed in sannō shintō sources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Buddhist ethical principles also apply (as deities are avatars of Buddhas and bodhisattvas)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

Notes: It is made known through oracles.

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Notes: Although in some sources the many supernatural beings are clearly framed as being emanated by one Buddha.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Disease or even death caused by wrath of deities, unfavourable rebirth can be a result of neglecting to worship them.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The wrath of the deities can result from an offense to their priests or to the Enryakuji monastics. The person incurring the wrath is not necessarily the one who has committed the offense in the first place. In the Heike monogatari, the regent Fujiwara no Moromichi falls ill as a result of the wrath of the sannō deities. The events leading to the disease are the following: 1. Fujiwara no Yoshitsuna, the governor of Mino province, kills an Enryakuji monk. 2. Some Hie shrine and Enryakuji temple officials petition to the imperial gates for Yoshitsuna's punishment. 3. The regent Fujiwara no Moromichi orders to disperse them. 4. Eight of them are killed. English translation of the episode in McCullough, Helen C., *The Tale of the Heike*, Stanford, California, Stanford University Press, 1988, pp. 49-50.

Reference: McCullough, Helen Craig. *The Tale of the Heike*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press, 2014.

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↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on sources, but the ones praising the benefic activity of the Hie deities as agents of Buddhas emphasise the blanket character of their benevolence, no matter how much of a desperate case the person seeking help is.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

Notes: Especially in Heian-period sources (794-1185).

Reference: Satō 佐藤, Masato 真人. ““heian Shoki Tendaishū No Shinbutsu Shūgō: Saichō to Ennin Wo Chūshin Ni” 平安初期天台宗の神仏習合思想—最澄と円珍を中心に—”. In *Umi Wo Wataru Tendai Bunka 海を渡る天台文*. Tōkyō: Bensei Shuppan, 2008.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the sense that there is an expectation for a future Buddha, Miroku, to eventually restore the prime of Buddhist teachings to the world. In the Yōtenki (12-15th century), he is identified as acting in the world as a bodhisattva under the guise of one of the Hie deities, Jūzenji. However, "messianic" beliefs are not emphasised in sannō shintō.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Alive in the sense that he is acting in this world as a bodhisattva under the guise of the Hie deity Jūzenji. He is not a Buddha yet, so has not fulfilled his eschatological role.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: If we broadly consider Buddhas messiahs. He is the Buddha who follows the historical one, Śākyamuni.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Political stability comes as an effect of religious stability.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: We might say there is an eschatology ONLY in the sense that Miroku exists. My answer is negative because there is no emphasis in the material on the coming of future Buddhas. Even more so because, within a context of correct worship, the Hie shrines are already, in the phenomenal world, a Buddhist Pure Land.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: But not emphasised.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See additional questions. It is important to note that virtues are not always expected to be upheld by those who worship at the Hie shrines. On the contrary, a certain kind of wretchedness is framed as expected from them. This is because 1. Discourses on the position of Japan in the Buddhist world at the time rather considered Japan a "desperate case", where the consciences of its inhabitants were unsuited to receive Buddhist teachings. This was because of their temporal and spatial distance from the "prime time" of Buddhism, when Śākyamuni was active in the world. Some discourses connected to sannō shintō (but not all) emphasise this first aspect. 2. The Hie shrine is framed (e.g. in the Yōtenki 12th-15th century) as being especially powerful because of its capacity to bring benefit to people who might be considered "hopeless", for instance because they are especially poor and cannot donate large amounts of money or because they have various physical issues as a result of their karmic hindrances.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– No

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as compassion is a primary Mahayana virtue it is highly emphasised, however it is mostly the compassion of the deities which is essential to achieve salvation.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

Notes: These are all virtues emphasised as belonging to the deities, but not necessarily required of the adherents.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Giving alms to the shrines grants benefits in this life or the next.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar selfless giving is a Mahayana principle.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual adherence: going to the Hie shrines and giving offers is seen as the way to obtain worldly and otherworldly benefits (for instance ensuring one a favourable rebirth in a Buddhist paradise). However, the ritual in question might be as simple as giving alms or offerings.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– No

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: These are more described as ideal outcome of worshipping the deities.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– No

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the mercy of the deities and the benefits they bestow are seen (and written about) as "something to be thankful for".

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Though it is a positive outcome of good karma and correct worship (e.g. in Yōtenki, 13-15th century).

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Notes: It depends. For priests at the shrine, ideally yes, but for worshippers, no.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Valuable goods offered to the shrines (money)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Visiting shrines is encouraged

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: General Buddhist ones apply.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1000

Notes: Sources mention participants in the thousands for sermons and festivals, however it is not confirmed whether the numbers are accurate.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If for a "large scale ritual" we intend the festivals, then the recurrence is annual. If we intend, for instance, Buddhist sermons which drew big crowds, it is harder to know. We do not have documentations for all the occurrences.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Many texts on Sannō shintō report many different "options" for the identity of a deity or the origin of a rite.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: But the Hafuribe priests at the Hie shrine employ actual kinship terminology, in the sense that they are a line of priesthood transmitted from father to son or from uncle to nephew.

Membership Costs and Practices

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Notes: But the Hafuribe priests at the Hie shrine employ actual kinship terminology, in the sense that they are a line of priesthood transmitted from father to son or from uncle to nephew.

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Enryakuji is an education facility for monastics.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Because of above.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: No ordination platform for nuns at Enryakuji.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Hie shrine is part of the broader Enryakuji administrative machine.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for instance the above mentioned passage toll. Low ranking priests affiliated to the Hie shrine enforced moneylending.

Reference: Gay, Suzanne Marie. *The Moneylenders of Late Medieval Kyoto*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2001.

Reference: Shimosaka 下坂, Mamoru 守. Chūsei Jiin Shakai to Minshū : Shuto to Bashaku Jinin Kawaramono 中世寺院社会と民衆 : 衆徒と馬借・神人・河原者. Kyōto: Shibunkakushuppan, 2014.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: Warrior monks at Enryakuji.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Enryakuji/Hie shrine have land holdings.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: There is a shrine-specific ritual calendar, but only in the sense that the dates for the deities' festival are fixed. The calendar used is the "civilian" one.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Enryakuji participated in the Genpei war (1180-1185).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Court, government.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Where water sources are present in the Enryakuji/Hie shrine's estates.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: If a road is in the Enryakuji/Hie shrine estate, which is authorised to exact tolls. However this is more linked to the general institutional context than with sannō shintō, which only constitutes one discursive area of it.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Tendai ordination platform is legally recognised by the polity. It is however more relevant for the wider institutional (Buddhist and Tendai) context than for sannō shintō, which is only a discursive area within it.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Enryakuji is an education facility for monastics.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Because of above.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: No ordination platform for nuns at Enryakuji.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Hie shrine is part of the broader Enryakuji administrative machine.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Court, government.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Where water sources are present in the Enryakuji/Hie shrine's estates.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: If a road is in the Enryakuji/Hie shrine estate, which is authorised to exact tolls. However this is more linked to the general institutional context than with sannō shintō, which only constitutes one discursive area of it.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for instance the above mentioned passage tolled. Low ranking priests affiliated to the Hie shrine enforced moneylending.

Reference: Gay, Suzanne Marie. *The Moneylenders of Late Medieval Kyoto*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2001.

Reference: Shimosaka 下坂, Mamoru 守. *Chūsei Jiin Shakai to Minshū : Shuto to Bashaku Jinin Kawaramono 中世寺院社会と民衆 : 衆徒と馬借・神人・河原者*. Kyōto: Shibunkakushuppan, 2014.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Tendai ordination platform is legally recognised by the polity. It is however more relevant for the wider institutional (Buddhist and Tendai) context than for sannō shintō, which is only a discursive area within it.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: Warrior monks at Enryakuji.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Enryakuji participated in the Genpei war (1180-1185).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: There is a shrine-specific ritual calendar, but only in the sense that the dates for the deities' festival are fixed. The calendar used is the "civilian" one.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Enryakuji/Hie shrine have land holdings.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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